

Tutorial note on GA Neural Networks*

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Abstract

This tutorial aims to give an introduction to neural computation with Clifford Geometric Algebra (GA) rounded off with some application examples. GA NNs (Clifford NNs) are unique in geometrically correct representation and computation with multi-dimensional geometric data. Attendants will learn to represent problems in GA, construct GA multi layer perceptrons (MLPs), and interpret the results. Recommended for everyone dealing with multi-dimensional data.

In the first half a general introduction to the basics of neural networks of real numbers will be given. This includes types of learning problems (from supervised to unsupervised), regression with linear weights, optimization, layered NNs, and error propagation.

The second part treats the foundations of GA-neural computation. Already number systems like complex numbers and quaternions have many neural network applications. We explain the construction of basic, vector (Clifford group) and spinor GA neurons, and GA MLPs. These have advantages for processing, optimization, and interpretation of data as (geometric) objects by GA NNs.

Finally an overview of practical applications of GA-neurons to geometric data analysis will round off the tutorial. This will illustrate how naturally and interpretatively GA-NNs can be used to represent and analyze geometric objects and their relationships. Some explicit examples will be introduced from diverse fields like feature recognition, biochemistry and meteorology.

Keywords: Clifford geometric algebra, multidimensional Neural Networks, Self Organizing Maps, Clifford Neuron, Spinor Neuron, GA MLP, geometric interpretation, molecular conformation, climate extremes

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1 First part: (real-valued) neural nets

1.1 Type of learning problems

In learning problems, a training dataset is given $\{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N\}$. Each input is $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^D$. There are the following three types of problems.

- Supervised learning

Regression: Given $\{(\mathbf{x}, t)\}$, answer $y(\mathbf{x})$ for new \mathbf{x} .

Classification: Given $\{(\mathbf{x}, \text{class})\}$, answer class for new \mathbf{x} .

In supervised learning, a continuous value $t \in \mathbb{R}$ or a categorical value “class” is given as a target correspondingly for each input.

- Unsupervised learning

Visualization: Given $\{\mathbf{x}\}$, answer $\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x})$ in a visible space (e.g. \mathbb{R}^2) for \mathbf{x} .

Clustering: Given $\{\mathbf{x}\}$, answer class for \mathbf{x} .

In unsupervised learning, the goal is to visualize similar data near and different data far in a visible space or to make clusters of similar data subset.

- Semi-supervised learning

– Given a labeled set $\{(\mathbf{x}, t)\}$ and an unlabeled set $\{\mathbf{x}\}$, answer $y(\mathbf{x})$ for \mathbf{x} .

– Given a labeled set $\{(\mathbf{x}, \text{class})\}$ and an unlabeled set $\{\mathbf{x}\}$, label \mathbf{x} .

1.2 Linear model for regression

A linear model uses a set of fixed basis functions $\phi(\mathbf{x}) = [\phi_0(\mathbf{x}), \dots, \phi_{M-1}(\mathbf{x})]^T$ and a set of *weight* parameters $\mathbf{w} = [w_0, \dots, w_{M-1}]^T$ to predict an output

$$y(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w}) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} w_j \phi_j(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{w}^T \phi(\mathbf{x}). \quad (1)$$

The output is linear with \mathbf{w} . On the other hand it is nonlinear with the input because the basis functions are nonlinear. Fixing the basis function $\phi_0(\mathbf{x}) \equiv 1$, the corresponding weight w_0 is regarded as a *bias* parameter.

Some frequently used sets of basis functions, in the case of univariate input $\mathbf{x} = x \in \mathbb{R}$, are

polynomial: $\phi_j(x) = x^j$,

Gaussian: $\phi_j(x) = \exp\{-\beta(x - \mu_j)^2\}$,

sigmoid: $\phi_j(x) = [1 + \exp\{-(x - \mu_j)/s\}]^{-1}$,

where $\beta(> 0)$: a precision parameter; μ_j : center of Gaussian functions, s : scale parameter of sigmoid functions.

1.3 Optimization of parameters

The error function

$$E(\mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N \{t_n - y(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{w})\}^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N \{t_n - \phi(\mathbf{x}_n)^T \mathbf{w}\}^2 \quad (2)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{t} - \Phi \mathbf{w})^T (\mathbf{t} - \Phi \mathbf{w}) \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{t} = [t_1, \dots, t_N]^T$. An $N \times M$ matrix $\Phi = [\phi(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, \phi(\mathbf{x}_N)]^T$ is called the *design matrix* of the linear model.

The derivative of the error function with regard to the weights

$$\nabla E = \frac{\partial E}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = \Phi^T (\mathbf{t} - \Phi \mathbf{w}) \quad (4)$$

should be zero at the optimal weight parameters \mathbf{w}_{opt} because eq. (3) is a convex quadratic optimization problem. Thus,

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{opt}} = (\Phi^T \Phi)^{-1} \Phi^T \mathbf{t}. \quad (5)$$

1.4 Limitations of linear models

- Choice of basis functions
- “Curse of dimensionality”

1.5 Layered neural nets

An example of layered neural nets is shown in the slide.

$$a_j = \sum_{i=0}^D w_{ji}^{(1)} x_i \quad (6)$$

where $x_0 \equiv 1$.

$$z_j = g(a_j) \quad (7)$$

where $g(\cdot)$ is called an activation function. In many studies a *logistic sigmoid function*

$$g(a) = \{1 + \exp(-a)\}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

is used for hidden units because its derivative is easily calculated

$$g'(a) = \frac{dg(a)}{da} = g(a)\{1 - g(a)\}. \quad (9)$$

The k -th output is

$$y_k = \sum_{j=0}^M w_{kj}^{(2)} z_j = \sum_{j=0}^M w_{kj}^{(2)} g \left(\sum_{i=0}^D w_{ji}^{(1)} x_i \right). \quad (10)$$

Writing the weights in the second layer $\mathbf{w}_k = [w_{k0}^{(2)}, \dots, w_{kM}^{(2)}]^T$ and those in the first layer $\mathbf{V} = \{\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_M\}$ where $\mathbf{v}_j = [w_{j0}^{(1)}, \dots, w_{jD}^{(1)}]^T$, the

flexible basis functions are $\phi(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{V}) = [\phi_0 \equiv 1, \phi_m(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{v}_m) = g(\mathbf{v}_m^T \mathbf{x}), m = 1, \dots, M]^T$. Then the network output is

$$y_k = \mathbf{w}_k^T \phi(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{V}). \quad (11)$$

More general network allowing skip-layer connections is written as

$$a_j = \sum_{i \in \text{pa}(j)} w_{ji} z_i, \quad (12)$$

$$z_j = g(a_j), \quad (13)$$

where $\text{pa}(j)$ shows a set of nodes from which a connection exists to the node j . If appropriate connections are set, some D nodes and other K nodes can be regarded as inputs and outputs, respectively.

1.6 Error back propagation

Optimal weight parameters in the second layer \mathbf{w}_k of eq. (11) can be obtained in the same way as eq. (5). However, $\Phi(\mathbf{V})$ is not constant and it depends on the weights in the first layer. Therefore \mathbf{w}_k and \mathbf{V} should be updated iteratively. For this purpose, there are two approaches. One is *batch learning* and the other is *epoch learning*. Batch learning uses all given data at the same time like eq. (5) possible in the case of linear model. Epoch learning uses each datum of the training set one by one. In this tutorial we talk mainly on epoch learning.

Let us go back to the error function of the K -variate output network.

$$E(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{n=1}^N E_n(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K \{t_{nk} - y_k(\mathbf{x}_n; \mathbf{w}_k, \mathbf{V})\}^2 \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{w} = [\mathbf{w}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{w}_K^T, \mathbf{v}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{v}_M^T]^T$, a vector which has all $\{w_{kj}^{(2)}\}$ and $\{w_{ji}^{(1)}\}$. The goal is to find \mathbf{w} such that

$$\nabla E = \mathbf{0} \quad (15)$$

and all eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix

$$\mathbf{H} = \nabla (\nabla E)^T, \quad H_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial w_i \partial w_j} \quad (16)$$

are positive, i.e. E is at least locally minimal. In epoch learning, a weight in the second layer is updated

$$w_{kj}^{(2)} \mapsto w_{kj}^{(2)} - \eta \frac{\partial E_n}{\partial w_{kj}^{(2)}} \quad (17)$$

where η is a hyper parameter called *learning rate*. If enough neurons and an appropriate value of η are provided, the error converges on zero after sufficient number of weight updates. The partial derivative with regard to the weight is calculated

$$\frac{\partial E_n}{\partial w_{kj}^{(2)}} = \frac{\partial E_n}{\partial y_k} \frac{\partial y_k}{\partial w_{kj}^{(2)}} = \underbrace{-(t_{nk} - y_k)}_{\text{error}_k} z_j. \quad (18)$$

A weight in the first layer is updated

$$w_{ji}^{(1)} \mapsto w_{ji}^{(1)} - \eta \frac{\partial E_n}{\partial w_{ji}^{(1)}}, \quad (19)$$

where the derivative is decomposed by the chain rule,

$$\frac{\partial E_n}{\partial w_{ji}^{(1)}} = \left(\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\partial E_n}{\partial y_k} \frac{\partial y_k}{\partial z_j} \right) \frac{\partial z_j}{\partial a_j} \frac{\partial a_j}{\partial w_{ji}^{(1)}} \quad (20)$$

$$= \underbrace{\left(\sum_k \text{error}_k w_{kj}^{(2)} \right)}_{\text{error}_j} g'(a_j) x_i. \quad (21)$$

Note that the *error* is propagated from output units to the middle unit backward as $\text{error}_j = g'(a_j) \sum_k \text{error}_k w_{kj}$. Then the partial derivative is expressed by the product of the *error* of a node and the output of the other node.

The back propagation of error in a general neural network eqs. (12) and (13) is

$$\text{error}_j = g'(a_j) \sum_{k \in \text{ch}(j)} \text{error}_k w_{kj}, \quad (22)$$

where $\text{ch}(j)$ is a set of nodes to which a connection exists from the node j . And the weights are updated

$$w_{ji} \mapsto w_{ji} - \eta \text{error}_j z_i. \quad (23)$$

1.7 Regularization of neural nets

To prevent *over-fitting*, a term is introduced to the error function

$$\tilde{E}(\mathbf{w}) = E(\mathbf{w}) + \lambda \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{w}. \quad (24)$$

The second term penalizes useless parameters (and corresponding connections between nodes). If a connection contributes to decrease $E(\mathbf{w})$ well, the connection deserves w with large norm.

1.8 Bayesian view of regularization

Assuming the target value has Gaussian noise with variance $\sigma^2 = \beta^{-1}$ where β is called precision parameter, a conditional probability density of t given \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{w}

$$p(t|\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w}, \beta) = \mathcal{N}(t|y(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w}), \beta^{-1}). \quad (25)$$

A probability of the dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{x}_n, t_n)\}$ given \mathbf{w} and β is

$$p(\mathcal{D}|\mathbf{w}, \beta) = \prod_{n=1}^N \mathcal{N}(t_n|y(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{w}), \beta^{-1}). \quad (26)$$

On the other hand, we assume a Gaussian prior distribution in parameter space with precision parameter α ,

$$p(\mathbf{w}|\alpha) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{w}|\mathbf{0}, \alpha^{-1}I). \quad (27)$$

Applying the Bayes theorem, a posterior probability is calculated

$$p(\mathbf{w}|\mathcal{D}, \alpha, \beta) \propto p(\mathcal{D}|\mathbf{w}, \beta)p(\mathbf{w}|\alpha). \quad (28)$$

Its logarithm becomes

$$\ln p(\mathbf{w}|\mathcal{D}, \alpha, \beta) = -\frac{\beta}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N \{t_n - y(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{w})\}^2 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{w} + \text{const.} \quad (29)$$

Note that maximizing this likelihood is equivalent to minimizing eq.(24) with $\lambda = \alpha/\beta$.

1.9 Sandglass neural net

Neural nets for supervised problems are described above. Neural nets for unsupervised problems are described in this and next subsections. In unsupervised learning, target value t is not given for each input \mathbf{x} . The aim is to find $\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^M$ in the visible space, where $M \leq 3$, so that more similar pair of inputs has mutually nearer positions in the visible space.

Sandglass neural net is one of the methods to visualize similarity among $\{\mathbf{x}\}$ in the visible space. It uses \mathbf{x} itself as a target signal. Applying the error back-propagation, activations of M hidden units become coordinates in the visible space.

1.10 Self-organizing map

Another type of neural nets for unsupervised learning is self-organizing maps (SOM). The second layer of SOM is composed of M dimensional grid. Now let us assume $M = 1$. The output of j -th unit is

$$z_j = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{w}_j\|^2 \quad (30)$$

The best match unit (BMU) b whose activation is the smallest is found.

$$b = \arg \min_j z_j \quad (31)$$

The weights corresponding to the BMU are updated as

$$\mathbf{w}_b \mapsto \mathbf{w}_b - \eta \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial \mathbf{w}_b} = (1 - \eta) \mathbf{w}_b + \eta \mathbf{x}. \quad (32)$$

Weights corresponding to the other units are updated as

$$\eta' = \varphi(|j - m|) \eta \quad (33)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_j \mapsto (1 - \eta') \mathbf{w}_j + \eta' \mathbf{x} \quad (34)$$

where φ is a monotoniously decreasing function.

2 Second part: Clifford geometric algebra neural networks

Already a variety of Clifford geometric algebra neural networks (GA NN) exist. For introductory literature we recommend [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. Geometric algebra support (multi)vector machines (GA SVMs) have also been studied [8], as well as recurrent Clifford NNs [9], and so-called Clifford Hopfield NNs [10].

For all types of Clifford GA NNs basic multivector calculus is essential [11, 12]. In many cases geometric calculations become particularly elegant using conformal geometric algebra [13, 14, 15].

We therefore first introduce some important results from multivector calculus.

2.1 Important multivector calculus

An important result of multivector differential calculus is given in Proposition 43 of [11] (see also [12])

$$(A * \partial_X)X = \dot{\partial}_X(\dot{X} * A) = P_{\text{subspace}}(A), \quad (35)$$

where $X = F(X)$ is the identity function on some linear subspace of $\mathcal{G}(I)$ of dimension d , and $P_{\text{subspace}}(A)$ is the projection into this d -dimensional subspace of $\mathcal{G}(I)$. I is the pseudoscalar of the geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}(I) = \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{p,q})$.

We can therefore prove the following lemma [16].

Lemma 1. *For any constant multivector $A \in \mathcal{G}(I)$*

$$\partial_X \langle X^{-1} A \rangle = -P_{\text{subspace}}(X^{-1} A X^{-1}). \quad (36)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_X \langle X^{-1} A \rangle &= \partial_X \langle X^{-1} X X^{-1} A \rangle \\ &= \dot{\partial}_X \langle \dot{X}^{-1} X X^{-1} A \rangle + \dot{\partial}_X \langle X^{-1} \dot{X} X^{-1} A \rangle + \dot{\partial}_X \langle X^{-1} X \dot{X}^{-1} A \rangle \\ &= 2\partial_X \langle X^{-1} A \rangle + \dot{\partial}_X \langle \dot{X} X^{-1} A X^{-1} \rangle \\ &= 2\partial_X \langle X^{-1} A \rangle + P_{\text{subspace}}(X^{-1} A X^{-1}). \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

In the last equality we have used (35). We conclude from (37) that

$$\partial_X \langle X^{-1} A \rangle = -P_{\text{subspace}}(X^{-1} A X^{-1}). \quad (38)$$

□

Based on Lemma 1 we derive the following theorem [16].

Theorem 1. *For any two constant multivectors $A, B \in \mathcal{G}(I)$ and $A' = X A X^{-1}$ we have*

$$\partial_X \langle X A X^{-1} B \rangle = \partial_X \langle A' B \rangle = P_{\text{subspace}}(X^{-1} [A' B - B A']). \quad (39)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
\partial_X \langle XAX^{-1}B \rangle &= \dot{\partial}_X \langle \dot{X}AX^{-1}B \rangle + \dot{\partial}_X \langle \dot{X}^{-1}BXA \rangle \\
&= P_{\text{subspace}}(AX^{-1}B) - P_{\text{subspace}}(X^{-1}BXAX^{-1}) \\
&= P_{\text{subspace}}(X^{-1}XAX^{-1}B - X^{-1}BXAX^{-1}) \\
&= P_{\text{subspace}}(X^{-1}[A'B - BA']). \tag{40}
\end{aligned}$$

For the second equality we have used (35) and Lemma 1. \square

An alternative form of Theorem 1 is given in the following corollary.

Corollary 1. *For any two constant multivectors $A, B \in \mathcal{G}(I)$ and $A' = XAX^{-1}$, $B'' = X^{-1}BX$ we have*

$$\partial_X \langle A'B \rangle = \partial_X \langle AB'' \rangle = \partial_X \langle B''A \rangle = P_{\text{subspace}}([AB'' - B''A]X^{-1}). \tag{41}$$

Proof. Using the cyclic symmetry of the scalar product we find that

$$\langle A'B \rangle = \langle XAX^{-1}B \rangle = \langle AX^{-1}BX \rangle = \langle AB'' \rangle = \langle B''A \rangle. \tag{42}$$

To further prove the identity of the right hand sides of (39) and (41) we use $XX^{-1} = X^{-1}X = 1$.

$$\begin{aligned}
X^{-1}[A'B - BA'] &= X^{-1}[XAX^{-1}B1 - BXAX^{-1}] \\
&= [AX^{-1}BXX^{-1} - X^{-1}BXAX^{-1}] \\
&= [AB'' - B''A]X^{-1}. \tag{43}
\end{aligned}$$

\square

2.2 Basic Clifford Neurons (BCN)

Because every Clifford geometric algebra is a generalization of the real numbers, a Clifford GA neuron should therefore generalize a real neuron. For simplicity we consider the most common real neuron of perceptron-type with the identity as activation function. This real neuron computes a weighted sum of its inputs x_i according to

$$y = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + \theta. \tag{44}$$

Using instead multivector weights $w_i \in Cl(p, q)$, a multivector threshold $\theta \in Cl(p, q)$ and replacing real multiplication by the geometric product readily turns (44) into a Clifford neuron, which computes a function from $(Cl(p, q))^n$ to $Cl(p, q)$. Note that for $Cl(0, 0)$, of course, one gets the real neuron back again.

A Basic Clifford Neuron [1, 2] is the atom of Clifford neural computation.

Definition 1 (Basic Clifford Neuron (BCN)). *A Basic Clifford Neuron, $BCN_{p,q}$, computes the following function from $Cl(p, q)$ to $Cl(p, q)$*

$$y = wx + \theta. \tag{45}$$

A BCN has only one multivector input and therefore also only one multivector weight but it does process multidimensional entities (for $p + q > 0$). The general update rule using gradient descent for a BCN with simplified, for notation purposes, error function

$$E = \|error\|^2 := \|d - y\|^2, \quad (46)$$

where d stands for desired output, reads

$$\Delta w = -\partial_w E = 2error \tilde{x}, \quad (47)$$

where $\tilde{\cdot}$ denotes principal involution, as given in equations (66) to (69) using overbar notation instead. The complete dynamics of a BCN can be derived by an eigenanalysis of its Hessian matrix. The threshold θ of a BCN is a generic parameter in the sense, that it does not depend on the signature (p, q) of the underlying Clifford algebra. In what follows we therefore only study Hessians w.r.t. the multivector weight w .

Theorem 2 (Hessian of a BCN). *The elements of the Hessian matrix $\mathbf{H}_{\text{BCN}_{p,q}}$ of a $\text{BCN}_{p,q}$ are given by*

$$\partial_{IJ} E = \partial_{JI} E = \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_J \partial w_I} = 2 \langle \tilde{e}_I e_J x \tilde{x} \rangle \quad (48)$$

where $\tilde{\cdot}$ denotes principal involution.

A proof of this theorem can be found in [3]. The theorem states that for every I, J the scalar component of the product resulting from multiplying $\tilde{e}_I e_J$ with the multivector $x \tilde{x}$ is "picked out". Consequently, one gets easily the following result for the neurons $\text{BCN}_{0,q}$.

Corollary 2. *The Hessian of a $\text{BCN}_{0,q}$ is a scalar matrix aE , where E denotes the identity matrix.*

This means that the error surface of a $\text{BCN}_{0,q}$ is isotropic. Hence batch learning converges in one step if the optimal learning rate is used. Note that both the case of the complex $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$ and the case of the quaternionic $\text{BCN}_{0,2}$ are covered by the corollary.

We now have a closer look at the $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$ and the $\text{BCN}_{1,0}$.

It is well known that complex multiplication is equivalent to a rotation and a scaling. Hence the whole propagation function of a $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$ can be illustrated as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Illustration of the propagation function of the complex $BCN_{0,1}$.

A typical error surface of a $BCN_{0,1}$ is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Typical error surface of the complex $BCN_{0,1}$.

The matrix representation of a multivector $x = x_0 + x_1 e_1 \in \mathcal{C}_{1,0}$ of unit norm has matrix representation

$$x = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon \cosh(\phi) & \epsilon \sinh(\phi) \\ \epsilon \sinh(\phi) & \epsilon \cosh(\phi) \end{pmatrix} \quad (49)$$

for some $\phi \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\epsilon = \pm 1$. Hence multiplication in $\mathcal{C}_{1,0}$ is equivalent to a hyperbolic rotation and a scaling. The resulting propagation function of a $BCN_{1,0}$ is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Illustration of the propagation function of the hyperbolic $BCN_{1,0}$.

The error surface of a $BCN_{1,0}$ is not isotropic. It is characterized by elliptic contour lines which are rotated about 45 degrees w.r.t. the origin (see Fig. 4). This follows directly from (48).

Figure 4: Typical error surface of the hyperbolic $BCN_{1,0}$.

In general, the propagation function of a BCN is not equivalent to a (not necessarily Euclidean) rotation, scaling and translation. Such a decomposition, however, can be realized by a second type of Clifford neuron.

2.3 Quaternion spinor neuron

The algebra of quaternions $\mathbb{H} \cong \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{0,2})$ is a division algebra. This eases a number of calculations. But due to their inherent non-commutativity quaternion NNs have many essential features of higher order Clifford GA NNs, besides having many interesting applications [1, 6].

The scalar positive definite *error function* of a quaternion spinor neuron (QSN) can be defined [1] as

$$E = \frac{1}{2}(D - Y)\overline{(D - Y)}, \quad (50)$$

where $D \in \mathbb{H}$ represents a given target value, overbar the quaternion conjugation, and $Y \in \mathbb{H}$ the node computation

$$Y = WX\overline{W} + \Theta, \quad (51)$$

dependent on the node input $X \in \mathbb{H}$, the weight $W \in \mathbb{H}$ and the node threshold $\Theta \in \mathbb{H}$. Inserting Y in E gives

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \frac{1}{2}(D - \Theta - WX\overline{W})\overline{(D - \Theta - WX\overline{W})} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(D - \Theta)\overline{(D - \Theta)} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}[WX\overline{W}\overline{(D - \Theta)} + (D - \Theta)\overline{(WX\overline{W})}] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2}WX\overline{W}\overline{WX\overline{W}}. \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

All three terms on the right hand side of the second equality are scalars. The second term has the structure

$$-\frac{1}{2}\langle q + \overline{q} \rangle = -\langle q \rangle, \quad q = WX\overline{W}\overline{(D - \Theta)}, \quad (53)$$

where $\langle q \rangle$ indicates the scalar part of $q \in \mathbb{H}$. The first term is independent of the weight W , we therefore have zero weight derivative

$$\frac{1}{2}\partial_W(D - \Theta)\overline{(D - \Theta)} = 0. \quad (54)$$

The derivative of the second term can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} -\partial_W\langle WX\overline{W}\overline{(D - \Theta)} \rangle &= -\dot{\partial}_W\langle \dot{W}X\overline{W}\overline{(D - \Theta)} \rangle - \dot{\partial}_W\langle \overline{W}X\overline{(D - \Theta)}WX \rangle \\ &= -X\overline{W}\overline{(D - \Theta)} - \dot{\partial}_W\langle \overline{W}X(D - \Theta)\dot{W} \rangle \\ &= -X\overline{W}\overline{(D - \Theta)} - \dot{\partial}_W\langle \dot{W}\overline{W}X(D - \Theta) \rangle \\ &= -X\overline{W}\overline{(D - \Theta)} - \overline{W}X(D - \Theta), \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

where we have used (35) in equalities one and four, and for equalities two and three that for quaternions $p, q \in \mathbb{H}$

$$\overline{pq} = \overline{q}\overline{p}, \quad \langle pq \rangle = \langle qp \rangle, \quad \langle q \rangle = \langle \overline{q} \rangle. \quad (56)$$

Using (35) for quaternions makes the projection of (35) superfluous, because it is the projection to the whole space of quaternions. Finally we calculate the derivative of the third term of E as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \partial_W W X \overline{W} \overline{W X \overline{W}} &= \frac{2}{2} \dot{\partial}_W \langle \dot{W} X \overline{W} \overline{W X \overline{W}} \rangle + \frac{2}{2} \dot{\partial}_W \langle W X \overline{W} \overline{W X \overline{W}} \rangle \\ &= X \overline{W} \overline{W X \overline{W}} + \overline{W X} (W X \overline{W}), \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

where we have again used (35), and that with (56) the second term on the right side of the first equality of (57) can be rearranged to

$$\langle W X \overline{W} \overline{W X \overline{W}} \rangle = \langle \dot{W} \overline{W X} W X \overline{W} \rangle. \quad (58)$$

Combining the results of (55) and (57) we finally get

$$\partial_W E = -X \overline{W} \overline{[(D - \Theta) - \overline{W X \overline{W}}]} - \overline{W X} [D - \Theta - W X \overline{W}]. \quad (59)$$

If in addition we define the computation error of the node to be

$$error = D - Y = D - \Theta - W X \overline{W}, \quad (60)$$

we can rewrite the derivative of the error function as

$$\begin{aligned} -\partial_W E &= X \overline{W} \overline{error} + \overline{W X} error \\ &= \overline{error W X} + \overline{W X} error. \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

This last form of $-\partial_W E$ is very concise and suitable for constructing optimal weight update rules for neural networks with QSN nodes [1, 3]

$$\Delta W = -\eta \partial_W E, \quad (62)$$

with constant $0 < \eta \in \mathbb{R}$.

A number of numerical experiments comparing the performance of conventional real linear associator NNs and QSNs are explained in [1].

2.4 Conformal GA versor (Lipschitz) neurons

QSN nodes are excellent for implementing rotations in 3D space. But the more general form of geometric algebra, the so-called conformal model of Euclidean geometry in $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{4,1})$ is often more suitable to express geometric entities and their relationships. Conformal geometric algebra allows to implement rotoinversions (alias roto-reflections), screw motions, dilations, and transversions in Euclidean space in a very analogous way by general versor (Lipschitz element, Clifford group) transformations. These transformations include therefore reflections at arbitrary planes, rotations around arbitrary axis, translations, central expansions (or contractions), and inversions relative to any point. Neural networks with these nodes will therefore be ideally suited to learn these transformations with high accuracy and efficiency.

The conformal model of 3D Euclidean geometry is formulated in the so-called conformal geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$, where the basic Euclidean

vector space \mathbb{R}^3 needs to be expanded to the non-Euclidean 5D space $\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1}$ [13, 14, 15] with orthonormal basis

$$\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_+, \mathbf{e}_-\}, \quad \mathbf{e}_1^2 = \mathbf{e}_2^2 = \mathbf{e}_3^2 = \mathbf{e}_+^2 = -\mathbf{e}_-^2 = 1. \quad (63)$$

Conformal blades $B \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$ describe elementary geometric objects, like points, point pairs, circles, spheres, lines and planes. Conformal (Lipschitz element) versors V describe in conformal Clifford group (see e.g. [19], p. 220) representations the above mentioned transformations of arbitrary conformal multivectors $X \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$

$$X' = (-1)^v V^{-1} X V, \quad (64)$$

where the versor is a geometric product of v *invertible* vectors $\in \mathbb{R}^{3+1,1}$.

As for the QSN in (51), we now study a conformal versor (transformation) neuron (CVN) [17] with input multivectors $X \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$, weight versors $W \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$, and multivector thresholds $\Theta \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$ by

$$Y = (-1)^w W^{-1} X W + \Theta. \quad (65)$$

For constructing the conformal error function, we further need the *principal involution*. We also use the overbar symbol, but this will not lead to confusion, because in the case of pure rotations in 3D around the origin, the principal involution of a rotor (1:1 isomorphic to quaternions) specializes to quaternion conjugation. The principal involution of the basis vectors (63) is defined as

$$\overline{\mathbf{e}_1} = \mathbf{e}_1, \quad \overline{\mathbf{e}_2} = \mathbf{e}_2, \quad \overline{\mathbf{e}_3} = \mathbf{e}_3, \quad \overline{\mathbf{e}_+} = \mathbf{e}_+, \quad \overline{\mathbf{e}_-} = -\mathbf{e}_-, \quad (66)$$

i.e. we always multiply with the sign of the quadratic form in (63). By linearity the principal involution of any vector $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{3+1,1}$ is

$$\overline{\mathbf{X}} = \sum_{l=1}^{l=-} X_l \overline{\mathbf{e}_l} = X_1 \mathbf{e}_1 + X_2 \mathbf{e}_2 + X_3 \mathbf{e}_3 + X_+ \mathbf{e}_+ - X_- \mathbf{e}_-. \quad (67)$$

The principal involution of a versor is defined as the principal involution of its vector factors followed by reversion of the order of all vector factors

$$\overline{\overline{a_1 a_2 \dots a_k}} = \overline{a_k} \dots \overline{a_2} \overline{a_1}, \quad a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k \in \mathbb{R}^{3+1,1}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0. \quad (68)$$

All multivectors are linear combinations of blades, and all blades are versors. The linearity of the above definition of the principal involution therefore allows to extend the definition of the principal involution from versors to arbitrary conformal multivectors [18]. Due to the use of the reversion, the principal involution is an anti-involution

$$\overline{\overline{X}} = X, \quad \overline{XY} = \overline{Y} \overline{X}, \quad \forall X, Y \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1}). \quad (69)$$

The principal involution does not change the grade of a multivector expression, grade extraction and principal involution commute therefore

$$\overline{\langle X \rangle_k} = \langle \overline{X} \rangle_k, \quad \forall X \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1}), \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N}_0, 0 \leq k \leq 5. \quad (70)$$

Scalars are invariant under the principal involution

$$\bar{\alpha} = \alpha, \quad \forall \alpha \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (71)$$

We therefore get the useful identities

$$\langle \bar{X}Y \rangle = \langle Y\bar{X} \rangle = \overline{\langle Y\bar{X} \rangle} = \langle \overline{Y\bar{X}} \rangle = \langle X\bar{Y} \rangle = \langle \bar{Y}X \rangle, \quad \forall X, Y \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1}). \quad (72)$$

The use of the principal involution has the distinct advantage that the scalar product of any multivector $X \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$ with its principal involution $\bar{X} \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$ is positive definite:

$$\langle X\bar{X} \rangle = \langle \bar{X}X \rangle \geq 0, \quad \langle X\bar{X} \rangle = 0 \Leftrightarrow X = 0. \quad (73)$$

We therefore define the conformal error function of a CVN as

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \langle (D - Y)\overline{(D - Y)} \rangle, \quad (74)$$

where $D \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$ represents a target output multivector for the CVN calculation. For later use we define the conformal error multivector again as

$$error = D - Y. \quad (75)$$

Inserting (65) the conformal error function becomes

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \frac{1}{2} \langle (D - (-1)^w W^{-1} X W - \Theta)\overline{(D - (-1)^w W^{-1} X W - \Theta)} \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \langle (D - \Theta)\overline{(D - \Theta)} \rangle \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle (-1)^w W^{-1} X W \overline{(D - \Theta)} \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle (D - \Theta)\overline{(-1)^w W^{-1} X W} \rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \langle W^{-1} X W \overline{W^{-1} X W} \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \langle (D - \Theta)\overline{(D - \Theta)} \rangle \\ &\quad - \langle (-1)^w W^{-1} X W \overline{(D - \Theta)} \rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \langle W^{-1} X W \overline{W^{-1} X W} \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

using (72) for the third equality. Because the first term on the right hand side of (76) is independent of the multivector weight W , its multivector derivative with respect to W vanishes

$$\partial_W \frac{1}{2} \langle (D - \Theta)\overline{(D - \Theta)} \rangle = 0. \quad (77)$$

Using Corollary 1 we can now calculate the weight multivector derivative of the second term of the conformal error function (76) as

$$\begin{aligned} &- \partial_W \langle (-1)^w W^{-1} X W \overline{(D - \Theta)} \rangle \\ &= P_{SW} \left([(-1)^w W^{-1} X W \overline{(D - \Theta)} - \overline{(D - \Theta)}(-1)^w W^{-1} X W] W^{-1} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (78)$$

where P_{SW} indicates projection to the particular subspace of $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{3+1,1})$ from which W is chosen.

For the calculation of the weight multivector derivative of the third term of the conformal error function (76) we again use Corollary 1

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_W \frac{1}{2} \langle W^{-1} X W \overline{W^{-1} X W} \rangle \\ &= -P_{SW} \left([(W^{-1} X W \overline{W^{-1} X W} - \overline{W^{-1} X W} W^{-1} X W] W^{-1}) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

Combining the results of (77), (78) and (79) we finally get for the the weight multivector derivative of the full conformal error function (76)

$$\begin{aligned} -\partial_W E &= -P_{SW} \left([(-1)^w W^{-1} X W \overline{(D - \Theta - (-1)^w W^{-1} X W)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \overline{D - \Theta - (-1)^w W^{-1} X W} (-1)^w W^{-1} X W] W^{-1} \right) \\ &= P_{SW} \left([\overline{error} (-1)^w W^{-1} X W - (-1)^w W^{-1} X W \overline{error}] W^{-1} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (80)$$

The concise form of (80) is suitable for deriving optimal weight update rules for neural networks with CVN nodes

$$\Delta W = -\eta \partial_W E, \quad 0 < \eta \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (81)$$

The optimal value of the constant η is related to the Hesse matrix of E . For basic Clifford neurons the optimal value is [1, 3]

$$\eta_{opt} = \frac{1}{\lambda_{max}}, \quad (82)$$

where λ_{max} is the biggest eigenvalue of the Hesse matrix of the neuron under consideration. For CVN neurons the Hesse matrix may be invariantly computed as the matrix of all second order multivector differentials [11, 12]

$$(A * \partial_W)(B * \partial_W)E, \quad (83)$$

where for A and B all basis blades of the weight subspace of $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R}^{4,1})$ need to be inserted. Compare also eq. (48) for the BCN Hesse matrix.

2.5 The projection P_{SW} into the weight subspace

Care must be taken for the projection P_{SW} into the weight subspace, because for calculating this projection the subspace under consideration needs to both have a blade basis and a reciprocal blade basis [11, 12, 16]

$$P_{SW}(A) = \sum a^J \langle a_J A \rangle, \quad (84)$$

where the a_J constitute the subspace blade basis and the a^J the corresponding reciprocal blade basis of the same subspace.

For example if only rotations around the origin are considered the 4D rotor weight subspace (isomorphic to \mathbb{H}) has the basis

$$\{1, \mathbf{e}_{12}, \mathbf{e}_{23}, \mathbf{e}_{31}\}. \quad (85)$$

If only translations are considered the 7D translator weight subspace is spanned by

$$\{1, \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_0\}, \quad (86)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_0$ need to be included as the reciprocal bivectors of $\mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_\infty$.

If rotor and translator weights are required to be combined as so-called motor weights we need the 12D weight subspace

$$\{1, \mathbf{e}_{12}, \mathbf{e}_{23}, \mathbf{e}_{31}, \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_{123}\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_{123}\mathbf{e}_\infty\}. \quad (87)$$

3 Third part: Applications of geometric algebra neural networks

Already a variety of applications of Clifford geometric algebra neural networks (GA NN) exist. Examples can be found in [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. Geometric algebra support (multi)vector machines (GA SVMs) have also been applied in [8], as well as recurrent Clifford NNs [9], and so-called Clifford Hopfield NNs [10]. In the following we give some details, but because of lack of space we cannot give a comprehensive overview. The interested reader is referred to the literature for more details.

3.1 Numerical experiments for geometric problems

Reference [1] contains numerical experiments with NNs based on complex, hyperbolic and dual numbers. This includes detailed experimental comparisons with conventional linear associator NNs. Results are that NNs based on complex, hyperbolic and dual numbers learn rotations, hyperbolic transformations and shear transformations faster and with better noise performance than linear associators with the same number of degrees of freedom (DOF).

Reference [1] also shows experimentally that QSNs learn geometric transformations in 3D based on noisy data with much better accuracy than linear associator NNS with the same number of DOF.

Using a dual Clifford associator with dual number BCN nodes of 18 DOF leads to substantially better performance than a conventional linear associator with 36 DOF on a task of learning 3D lines subject to translations and rotations. Better results are obtained for the Clifford associator in all three categories of training performance with noise, training accuracy (less training errors), and test performance with noise. [1]

Clifford multilayer perceptrons lead to good complex function approximation. [1] On the task of 3D function extrapolation (example: Lorentz attractor) QSNs are shown to have superior results (52 DOF) compared with linear associator NNs (59 DOF). [1] The QSN results are better with respect to the number of parameters, noise performance and correlation.

Reference [9] studies the use of so-called recurrent Clifford support vector machines with applications to time series and tasks of visually guided robots.

Reference [10] introduces Clifford Hopfield NNs in order to construct a neurocomputing framework to build attractors in space and time for robot events.

Reference [21] studies various kinds of feature extraction from spatial data, involving GA NNs. It proposes to use geometric algebra to systematically extract geometric features from data given in a vector space. It shows results of classification of hand-written digits, which were classified by feature extraction with the proposed method.

3.2 Numerical experiments with quaternion NNs on color image compression, associative pattern storage, and conformation of molecules

Matsui et al [6] showed in numerical experiments that the quaternion-version of the Back Propagation (BP) algorithm achieves correct geometrical transformations in three-dimensional space, as well as in *color space for an image compression problem*, whereas real-valued BP algorithms fail. The quaternion neural network also performs superior in terms of convergence speed to a real-valued neural network with respect to the 3-bit parity check problem, as simulations show.

Matsui et al [7] have also used quaternion NNs for a number of interesting experimental studies of quaternion Hopfield NNs showing that text pattern association close to a stored pattern is possible.

Reference [20] applies quaternion NNs of self-organizing map (SOM) type to the conformation of organic macromolecules.

3.3 Experiments on optimization of GA NNs

Reference [3] features numerical simulations on the optimal learning rates of GA NNs. BCNs for the GA of the 2D Euclidean plane, BCNs operating with quaternions, BCNs of the GA of the Minkowski plane, and linear associator NNs are compared. Optimization leads for the BCNs to instant one-shot learning success. The error surfaces are pictured in detail as well. The effect of different learning rates is studied experimentally for BCNs for the GA of the 2D Euclidean plane.

3.4 Applications of conformal GA NNs

Reference [17] demonstrates experimentally how a conformal versor neuron can learn the inversion at a sphere by adapting its multivector weight versor. A detailed numerical comparison with a real-valued multilayer perceptron on the same task is given. Yet for this type of problem it becomes clear that in principle MLPs cannot learn (derive the parameters of an inversion sphere) the solution satisfactorily.

Reference [8] shows how to design kernels for support multivector machines involving the Clifford geometric product and the conformal geomet-

ric neuron. It presents the design of kernels for nonlinear support vector machines using the Clifford geometric algebra framework. The kernels involve the Clifford or geometric product making use of nonlinear mappings which map multi-vectors into higher dimensional geometric algebra. The conformal geometric neuron for geometric classification is introduced. Experiments are given to demonstrate the usefulness of the approach.

3.5 Ground penetrating radar for mine (exploratives) detection

A. Hirose [4] has done very interesting applications of complex NNs with arrays of antennas for detecting hidden objects like mines with ground penetrating radar. He was able to demonstrate experimentally on a mine test site in Cambodia, that even under extremely difficult soil conditions mine detection is thus possible under conditions where all other methods failed previously to detect the mines.

Remark: Please refer to tutorial slides for further applications.

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